

ISic0811

I.Sicily inscription 0811

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [τ]ῆς πρὸς πάντας ἀνθρώπ[ους]
2. [ε]ύνοίας πειραθέντε[ς]
3. [κ]αὶ τῆς ἀνυπερβ[λ]ήτου χρησ[τό]
4. [τ]ητος] μετασχόντες
5. [Δ]ομιτίου Λατρωνιανοῦ
6. [τ]οῦ λαμπρ(οτάτου) ἔπανο[ρθωτοῦ]
7. [ῆ]βουλή καὶ ὁ δῆμος
8. εὐν[οίας][---]
9. χάριν

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644905

EDR 140615
EDCS 41300112
PHI 140600
PHI 175754

Bibliography

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